

Study of Oxygen and Carbon Isotopic Equilibrium in Coexisting Dolomite-Calcite Pairs in Limestone

LALLAN SINGH, S. N. DAS

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-5

and

T. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, L. S. College, Muzaffarpur

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The isotopic analyses of dolomite and calcite fractions in Kajarhat limestone showed ΔO_{D-c}^{18} and ΔC_{D-c}^{13} to vary from -0.97 to 0.60 and -1.83 to 1.53 respectively. The study reveals that the dolomite fractions are, in general, enriched in C^{13} and depleted in O^{18} content relative to the calci fractions. The data suggest that the dolomite-calcite pairs must have been formed under nonisotopic equilibrium.

THE O^{18} and C^{13} variation studies of coexisting minerals provide some pertinent information regarding the nature and extent of the equilibrium formed between the two components. Clayton and Epstein¹ have studied a large number of quartz-calcite and quartz-dolomite, both in equilibrium and non-equilibrium, pairs. O'Neil and Epstein² have shown that the natural dolomite-calcite assemblages which have small fractionation value were not formed under isotopic equilibrium.

In the previous paper³ the variations in O^{18} and C^{13} in the limestones, associated with crystallised calcites, have led to the conclusion that the carbonates were crystallised under non-isotopic equilibrium. Several samples of lower Vindhyan Kajarhat limestones from different sections of Bhawnathpur area, in the district of Palamau, Bihar were studied by Singh *et al.*⁴ The irregular correlations between the δ values of carbon and oxygen have been attributed to different extents of dolomitisation and postdepositional changes in the samples. The X-ray analysis of the samples shows the relative ratio⁵ of both dolomite and calcite in the samples. Therefore, oxygen and carbon isotopic analyses of dolomite and calcite fractions of the above samples have been carried out separately with a view to examine the fractionation between dolomite and calcite, to determine the extent of equilibrium in co-existing pairs and to find the mode of formation of dolomite.

Experimental

The limestone samples were treated with 100% phosphoric acid according to the method described by McCrea⁶, modified by Sharma and Sharma⁷. The extraction of carbondioxide from both the

fractions were done according to the procedure described by Epstein *et al.*⁸. The first half hour reaction gave the carbondioxide from calcite whereas the remaining carbondioxide obtained after 72-90 hrs of reaction was from the dolomite fractions. The mass spectrometric analyses were carried on 60°-60°-RMS-19 double collecting Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometer in the department of chemistry, I.I.T., Kanpur. Isotopic data are reported in δ -terminology defined as :

$$\delta\text{‰} = \left[\frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{standard}}} - 1 \right] \times 1000$$

where R represents the O^{18}/O^{16} or C^{13}/C^{12} ratios. The delta values are corrected for instrumental effects⁹ and reported with respect to SMOW and PDB for oxygen and carbon respectively.

Results and Discussion

The isotopic data of the dolomite and calcite fractions of the limestones are given in Table 1. From the data it is clear that most of the dolomites are depleted in O^{18} with respect to calcite. The O^{18} enrichment of calcite over dolomite is in fact in accordance with similar observations made by Degens and Epstein¹⁰ and more recently by Clayton *et al.*¹¹ The isotopic data on C^{13} fractionation between dolomite and calcite showed that in most of the samples dolomites are richer in C^{13} as compared to the calcites. A similar trend has been observed, by Clayton *et al.*¹¹, for the carbonates from Coorong area of South Australia. The same behaviour has been reported earlier by Waber¹². Thus interpreting the isotopic data on the line of above workers, it can be safely inferred that the dolomite-calcite pairs have been deposited under non-isotopic equilibrium. The conclusion is supported from the

TABLE I—ISOTOPIC DATA FOR COEXISTING DOLOMITE AND CALCITE IN LIMESTONE SAMPLES

Sample	δO^{18}_C	δO^{18}_D	ΔO^{18}_{D-C}	δC^{13}_C	δC^{13}_D	ΔC^{13}_{D-C}
A-8	19.32±0.10	19.92±0.10	+0.60	-0.70±0.19	-0.69±0.08	+0.01
B-1	17.53±0.08	16.86±0.10	-0.67	-1.73±0.07	-0.20±0.01	+1.53
B-2	20.74±0.14	21.05±0.09	+0.31	-1.75±0.06	-0.92±0.04	+0.83
B-3	20.75±0.09	21.10±0.06	+0.35	-1.65±0.07	-1.02±0.06	+0.63
B-4	21.83±0.08	20.86±0.10	-0.97	-0.57±0.03	-0.56±0.05	+0.01
B-5	22.54±0.06	21.93±0.10	-0.61	-0.81±0.12	-0.11±0.08	+0.70
C-1	17.82±0.12	17.71±0.16	-0.11	-0.50±0.23	-2.33±0.19	-1.83
C-2	19.72±0.18	19.00±0.11	-0.72	-1.30±0.23	-2.13±0.12	-0.83
C-3	20.68±0.21	19.93±0.14	-0.75	-0.54±0.17	-1.43±0.14	-0.89
C-4	22.55±0.16	22.77±0.11	+0.22	-0.94±0.10	-0.33±0.23	+0.61

C = Calcite; D = Dolomite; $\Delta D-C = \delta$ dolomite- δ calcite; \pm = Average deviation of the three analyses.

Fig. 1. Plot of δC^{13} calcite and δC^{13} dolomite.

Fig. 2. Plot δO^{18} calcite and δO^{18} dolomite.

plots of δC^{13} and δO^{18} in figures 1 and 2. In case of equilibrium pairs all the points in both the figures should have been above the line due to higher δO^{18} and δC^{13} of the dolomite. In case of C^{13} (fig. 1), the points are almost equally distributed on either side of the line, whereas in the case of O^{18} (fig. 2) the points are mostly below the line.

The ΔO^{18}_{D-C} and ΔC^{13}_{D-C} are found to vary from -0.97 to 0.60 and -1.83 to 1.53 respectively. The average ΔO^{18} and ΔC^{13} values are of the order of -0.23 and 0.08 respectively, which may be regarded as zero. Thus the conclusion gets further support, because O'Neil and Epstein² have demonstrated that those dolomite-calcite pairs which show very small fractionation were not formed at isotopic equilibrium.

Therefore it can be concluded that the dolomite-calcite pairs were non-equilibrium formations i.e., dolomite and calcite are not congenetic in the sense of having been precipitated from the same solution, and as there are very small differences in ΔO^{18} and ΔC^{13} values, it is plausible that the dolomitisation might have occurred by solid state cation exchange from calcite precursor as suggested by Epstein *et al.*³.

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